

HOW TO GET RID OF UNSIGHTLY VEINS

EFFECTIVELY?

The appearance of spider veins is not what people want to see. While the discolored and swollen veins are unattractive, they can create medical problems. While varicose vein removal herbs, homeopathic treatments, and other natural remedies, may prevent or reduce existing varicose veins, they usually do not cure them or remove them. Or get **varicose [vein treatment near me long island](#)**.

The condition of spider veins usually develops on the thighs and the back of the calf. They are usually at least 3 millimeters in diameter and are normally itchy and painful. Excessive scratching can cause the appearance of open sores. Research has shown that women are afflicted with the condition more often than men, as are people over fifty years old. If you are suffering from these bulging veins, consult a **vein specialist near me South Shore**.

People who are overweight pass the extra weight in the abdomen to the veins in the legs and this causes them to become enlarged. Research suggests that the condition worsens when standing for extended periods of time. The veins are equipped with valves that will prevent blood from moving backward as it travels up the leg. A spider vein occurs when these valves weaken and fail. This results in blood traveling from the heart to leak back where it came from, creating a pool. The blood that collects is what causes the vein to stretch and discolor. When this occurs, the area becomes unsightly and unattractive, it will likely become necessary to look at options for varicose vein removal. Get **vein treatment near me on the long island** to eliminate unsightly veins.

Vein treatments near me:

Surgery is considered the best varicose vein removal treatment li when the condition has become severe. One method is called “**stripping**” and it requires the insertion of a flexible implant into the affected areas. When this implant is removed, the affected area will see a reduction. This treatment can normally be performed using only partial or local anesthesia.

A **vein specialist in Long island** may opt to use one of the two endogenous **varicose vein treatments on North Shore**. These methods are much less invasive than the traditional stripping method. The methods still require that a device be inserted into the vein and depending on which [vein treatment North Shore](#) is used, either a radio frequency or a diode laser is used to seal it. In either case, the treated area by a **vein doctor near me Lindenhurst** will simply turn into scar tissue. All traces normally fade within a few weeks. The patient does not require an overnight stay at the hospital and resumes normal activities the very next day.

The process of varicose vein removal can be uncomfortable and inconvenient. Since there is no known cure other than removing them, prevention is important. It is best to maintain a healthy weight and elevate your legs whenever possible when standing for long periods of time. Get plenty of exercises. If blood flow is slow, wearing compression stockings can improve the flow and relieve some pressure. When all is said and done, the best course of prevention is natural remedies and supplements.